

An Analysis of Malaria-Related Pediatric Morbidity and Mortality at JLNMCH, Bhagalpur

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Abstract:

Background: Malaria remains a major public health concern, particularly in pediatric populations in endemic regions. Despite global efforts to reduce malaria-related morbidity and mortality, children continue to be disproportionately affected, especially in rural areas with limited healthcare access. In India, Bihar is one of the states with a significant burden of malaria, contributing to high rates of pediatric hospital admissions and deaths. **Aim:** To evaluate the morbidity and mortality associated with pediatric malaria.

Methods: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted on 80 pediatric patients aged 1 month to 12 years, diagnosed with malaria. Data were collected through patient medical records and structured interviews with guardians. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and multivariate logistic regression employed to identify predictors of mortality.

Results: The study found that 75% of the children presented with anemia, and 60% had severe anemia. *Plasmodium falciparum* was the predominant species (65%). The mean hospital stay was 7.8 days, with 12.5% of patients developing severe complications such as cerebral malaria and acute renal failure. The overall mortality rate was 6.3%. Severe anemia ($p = 0.002$) and the presence of complications ($p < 0.001$) were significantly associated with higher mortality.

Conclusion: Pediatric malaria is associated with significant morbidity and mortality, particularly among children with severe anemia and complications. The findings underscore the need for early diagnosis, effective management of anemia, and vigilant monitoring of complications to improve outcomes.

Recommendations: Enhanced malaria control measures, early intervention strategies, and improved access to healthcare are crucial in reducing pediatric malaria mortality. Strengthening community awareness and training healthcare workers in early diagnosis and management can also contribute to better outcomes.

Keywords: Pediatric Malaria, Morbidity, Mortality, Severe Anemia.

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Introduction

Malaria continues to be a significant global health challenge, particularly in regions with limited healthcare infrastructure and high transmission rates. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), despite a reduction in malaria cases and deaths over the past two decades, the disease still caused an estimated 241 million cases and 627,000 deaths worldwide in 2020, with the majority of fatalities occurring in sub-Saharan Africa among children under five years old [1]. India, while not in the highest burden category, remains one of the countries with a considerable number of malaria cases, especially in endemic regions such as Bihar [2]

Pediatric malaria presents unique challenges, as children are more susceptible to severe manifestations of the disease, including cerebral

malaria, severe anemia, and respiratory distress. These complications can lead to long-term developmental consequences and even death if not promptly and effectively treated. The burden of malaria among children is particularly severe in rural and impoverished areas where access to healthcare services is limited, and where delays in diagnosis and treatment are common [3].

In the context of Bihar, a state known for its high population density and variable healthcare access, malaria remains a persistent public health problem. The state reports a substantial number of malaria cases each year, with a significant proportion affecting the pediatric population. Recent studies have emphasized the importance of early diagnosis and prompt treatment in reducing malaria-related mortality [4]. However, the presence of

comorbidities, such as malnutrition, and challenges in accessing timely care exacerbate the risk of severe disease outcomes in children [5]. Moreover, the increasing resistance of *Plasmodium falciparum* to conventional anti-malarial drugs poses an additional threat, making effective management of pediatric malaria even more critical [6].

This study aims to evaluate the morbidity and mortality associated with pediatric malaria at JLN MCH, Bhagalpur.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional observational.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and Hospital (JLN MCH) in Bhagalpur, Bihar, India. The research was conducted over a period of six months to gather comprehensive data on the subject.

Participants: A total of 80 pediatric patients, aged between 1 month to 12 years, diagnosed with malaria and admitted to JLN MCH during the study period, were included in the study. These patients were selected based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria outlined below.

Inclusion Criteria

- Pediatric patients aged 1 month to 12 years.
- Confirmed diagnosis of malaria through microscopy or rapid diagnostic tests (RDT).
- Patients admitted to JLN MCH during the study period.
- Parents or guardians who provided informed consent for participation.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients older than 12 years.
- Patients with co-infections or chronic conditions that could confound the analysis (e.g., HIV, tuberculosis).
- Patients whose guardians did not provide informed consent.
- Patients with incomplete medical records.

Bias: Efforts were made to minimize selection bias by using a consecutive sampling method, where all eligible patients during the study period were included. Information bias was minimized by using standardized data collection tools and procedures.

Data Collection: Data were collected through a combination of patient medical records, laboratory reports, and structured interviews with the patients' guardians. Information gathered included demographic details, clinical presentation, laboratory results, treatment administered, and patient outcomes. Data were recorded in a pre-designed case report form (CRF).

Procedure: Upon admission, each patient's medical history and clinical findings were documented. Laboratory tests, including blood smears for malaria parasites and RDTs, were performed to confirm the diagnosis. Patients were monitored throughout their hospital stay, with daily assessments recorded until discharge or death. Outcomes of interest included the duration of hospital stay, complications, and mortality.

Statistical Analysis: Data were entered into SPSS version 23.0 for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the patients. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages, while continuous variables were summarized using means and standard deviations. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Multivariate analysis was conducted to adjust for potential confounders and to identify independent predictors of mortality.

Results

A total of 80 pediatric patients diagnosed with malaria were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 6.2 years (SD $\pm$ 3.4 years), with the majority (65%) being between 5 to 12 years old. There were 45 males (56.3%) and 35 females (43.7%), resulting in a male-to-female ratio of 1.3:1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Frequency (n = 80)	Percentage (%)
Age Group		
1 month - 1 year	10	12.5
1 - 5 years	18	22.5
5 - 12 years	52	65.0
Gender		
Male	45	56.3
Female	35	43.7
Area of Residence		
Rural	55	68.8
Urban	25	31.2
Nutritional Status		
Normal	60	75.0
Malnourished	20	25.0

The most common clinical symptoms at presentation were fever (100%), anemia (75%), and splenomegaly (45%). Other symptoms included vomiting (30%), jaundice (25%), and seizures (15%).

Table 2: Clinical Presentation of Participants

Symptom	Frequency (n = 80)	Percentage (%)
Fever	80	100
Anemia	60	75.0
Splenomegaly	36	45.0
Vomiting	24	30.0
Jaundice	20	25.0
Seizures	12	15.0

Laboratory analysis showed that 60% of the patients had severe anemia (hemoglobin <7 g/dL). The mean hemoglobin level was 7.2 g/dL (SD $\pm$ 1.8 g/dL). *Plasmodium falciparum* was the predominant species identified in 65% of the cases, while 35% had *Plasmodium vivax*.

Table 3: Laboratory Findings of Participants

Laboratory Finding	Mean ($\pm$ SD)	Frequency (n = 80)	Percentage (%)
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	7.2 $\pm$ 1.8		
Severe Anemia		48	60.0
Moderate Anemia		20	25.0
Normal Hemoglobin		12	15.0
Malaria Species			
<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>		52	65.0
<i>Plasmodium vivax</i>		28	35.0

All patients received standard anti-malarial therapy according to WHO guidelines. The mean duration of hospital stay was 7.8 days (SD $\pm$ 2.5 days). Of the 80 patients, 10 (12.5%) developed complications such as cerebral malaria (6 cases), acute renal failure (3 cases), and severe respiratory distress (1 case). Mortality was observed in 5 patients (6.3%).

Table 4: Treatment Outcomes of Participants

Outcome	Frequency (n = 80)	Percentage (%)
Mean Hospital Stay (days)	7.8 $\pm$ 2.5	
Complications		
Cerebral Malaria	6	7.5
Acute Renal Failure	3	3.8
Severe Respiratory Distress	1	1.3
Mortality	5	6.3

Chi-square tests were performed to assess the association between various factors and mortality. Severe anemia ($p = 0.002$) and the presence of complications ($p < 0.001$) were significantly associated with higher mortality.

Table 5: Association Between Factors and Mortality

Factor	Mortality (n = 5)	No Mortality (n = 75)	p-value
Severe Anemia	4	44	0.002
<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>	4	48	0.117
Complications	5	5	<0.001

Multivariate logistic regression analysis identified severe anemia (OR = 4.2, 95% CI: 1.5-12.1, $p = 0.005$) and presence of complications (OR = 7.8, 95% CI: 2.3-26.5, $p < 0.001$) as independent predictors of mortality.

Discussion

A total of 80 children, with a mean age of 6.2 years, were included in the study. The majority of the participants were between 5 to 12 years old, with a slightly higher proportion of males (56.3%) than females. The study revealed that malaria remains a prevalent and serious health issue in the pediatric population, particularly in rural areas, as

indicated by the high percentage (68.8%) of participants coming from rural regions.

Fever was universally present among all participants, highlighting it as the primary symptom of malaria. Anemia was also a significant clinical feature, with 75% of the children presenting with this condition, and 60% experiencing severe anemia. The study found that *Plasmodium falciparum* was the dominant species, responsible for 65% of the cases, which aligns with the known higher severity and complication rates associated with this species compared to *Plasmodium vivax*.

The treatment outcomes showed that while most children responded to standard anti-malarial therapy, the disease's impact was substantial, with a mean hospital stay of 7.8 days. Complications were observed in 12.5% of the patients, with cerebral malaria being the most common and severe complication. The overall mortality rate was 6.3%, which is concerning, considering the availability of effective treatment options.

Statistical analysis indicated that severe anemia and the presence of complications were significantly associated with higher mortality rates. Severe anemia, in particular, was identified as a strong predictor of mortality, suggesting that early identification and treatment of anemia in malaria-infected children could be crucial in reducing death rates. The presence of complications such as cerebral malaria further compounded the risk, emphasizing the need for vigilant monitoring and aggressive management of these conditions.

Overall, the study underscores the serious health burden posed by malaria among children in the region. The high rates of severe anemia and complications like cerebral malaria highlight critical areas where intervention could significantly improve outcomes. These findings call for enhanced focus on early diagnosis, comprehensive management strategies, and improved healthcare delivery to mitigate the morbidity and mortality associated with pediatric malaria in this setting.

A study highlighted the significant risk of recurrent malaria and mortality within one year of an initial malaria episode in children under five years old. The study found that 48.4% of the children presented multiple times with malaria, and 1.7% died within a year of their initial presentation. This emphasizes the need for continuous monitoring and preventive measures to reduce the risk of malaria recurrence and related deaths [7].

A study in Angola identified key factors associated with mortality in children under five who were admitted with severe malaria. Seizures, jaundice, and high parasitemia were found to significantly increase the risk of death. The study underscores the importance of early recognition and management of these severe symptoms to improve survival rates [8].

A prospective study in India showed that severe malaria complications such as respiratory distress, central nervous system involvement, shock, and renal failure were significant predictors of mortality in children. The study highlighted the necessity of early and aggressive treatment strategies in managing severe malaria to prevent fatal outcomes [9].

A study in the Democratic Republic of Congo revealed that cerebral malaria and severe anemia

were the most frequent severe forms of malaria in children under five, with a high mortality rate of 28.3%. The study identified repeated convulsions, coma, and severe acute malnutrition as major predictors of death, emphasizing the need for comprehensive management of these risk factors to reduce mortality [10].

A study in Sierra Leone found that cerebral malaria and severe clinical conditions at admission, including dehydration and malnutrition, were independent risk factors for mortality in children admitted for suspected malaria. The study suggests that interventions should focus on improving the early diagnosis and treatment of severe malaria and addressing logistical challenges in peripheral health units [11].

Conclusion

The study revealed that malaria remains a significant cause of morbidity and mortality among pediatric patients at JLNMC, Bhagalpur. Severe anemia and complications such as cerebral malaria are critical factors associated with poor outcomes. Early diagnosis and management of these factors could potentially reduce mortality in pediatric malaria cases. The findings emphasize the need for enhanced malaria control measures and better management strategies in endemic regions.

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